

Micro-determination of Manganese in Plant and Food Material

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Manganese is an essential constituent of all plant and animal tissues and it affects the growth when present in different amounts. There is evidence to indicate that the element is involved in activating several enzymes. The amount of Mn in foods varies considerably from 5 ppm to 1,000 ppm.

It has been reported by Keyworth¹ that N, N, N', N', tetrakis (2-hydroxy-propyl) ethylene diamine (THPED) forms coloured chelates with Cu⁺⁺, Zn⁺⁺, Ni⁺⁺, Pb⁺⁺, Co⁺⁺, Hg⁺⁺. and Ag⁺. This reaction was further investigated by Pike and Yoe³ who observed that a soluble pink coloured manganese THPED -Chelate was formed which showed good stability and maximum absorbance at pH 6.0±0.2. These workers, however, did not investigate the applicability of this reaction to the determination of Mn in the solution containing less than 2 ppm of Mn. An attempt has, therefore, been made to develop a procedure which could be applied to the analysis of agricultural products whose Mn content falls within this range and also which contains interfering cations in the formation of Mn-THPED Chelate. The method is free from interference upto 400 ppm each of Cu⁺⁺ and Zn⁺⁺ and most other cations when Mn is present upto 40 ppm. Pike and Yoe³ have similarly investigated the interference of 76 different ions and have reported that these cations do not interfere upto 10 fold excess of Mn. The plant and food materials contain these elements namely, Cu⁺⁺, Zn⁺⁺ not in ten fold excess of manganese.

In the present communication is described a method in which only 400-500 mg of the plant material is required for its combustion in the presence of oxygen gas, the products of combustion being absorbed in 6*N*-HCl. The periodate method is more laborious and requires digestion with mixtures of HNO₃, H₂SO₄ and H₃PO₄ which results in the production of large amounts of hazardous fumes. The proposed method is, however, rapid safe and more sensitive as compared to other methods. The sensitivity of this method is 1.24 parts of manganese in ten million parts of the solution. Reproducible results are obtained if the colour is produced under identical conditions. Factors like pH of the medium, order of addition of reagents and the time of taking the reading by a colorimeter should be strictly controlled.

Material :

1. 4*N* HCl., 6*N* HCl and 10*N* HCl.
2. Sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer pH 4.80— Mix 62.5 g of sodium acetate in distilled water, add 60 ml of glacial acetic acid and make the volume to 500 ml.

1. D. A. Keyworth, *Talanta*, 1959, **2**, 383.
2. F. Nelson, T. Murase and K. A. Kraus, *Chromatography*, 1964, **13** (2), 503-525.
3. L. Pike, and J. H. Yoe, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1964, **31**, 318-324.

3. 0.3 *M* N, N, N', N', tetrakis (2-hydroxy propyl) ethylene diamine (THPED): Dissolve 8.76 g of it and 11.20 g of KOH (AR) in distilled water and make the volume to 100 ml.

4. Manganese sulphate. $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (A.R.)

Apparatus:

1. Spectronic-20 Bausch and Lomb Colorimeter.
2. Beckmann Zeromatic pH meter.
3. Ion Exchange Column.

Fit up a resin column made from pyrex glass burette 225 mm long and 1.5 cm in diameter. Place $\frac{1}{2}$ inch layer of glass wool at the bottom and pour down the slurry consisting of Dowex-50W-X8 mesh (H^+ -form) resin suspended in water so that the resin column measures about 130 mm. Wash the column first with 10*N* HCl and then with deionized water. Repeat this process 3 to 4 times. The resin column is now ready. Regenerate the column each time with 4*N* HCl and wash it completely with distilled water. The column when not in use should always be kept moist with distilled water which should stand about 5-6 cm on its top. It should also be free from any air bubbles.

Procedure:

An accurately weighed sample of plant or food material (60 mesh) was placed in the middle of a filter paper carrier, folded, weighed accurately and then fitted in the platinum holder. 5 ml of 6*N* HCl as the absorbing liquid was taken in the flask and it was flushed with oxygen for 30 seconds (fig. 1). The wick was ignited and the stopper quickly inserted. The flask was tilted and held in the inverted position for another minute after the combustion of the sample. The flask was then allowed to stand for 30 minutes and shaken occasionally. The extract was taken out and then heated to dryness on a water bath. The residue was extracted with water and transferred to a 10 ml measuring flask. To this was added 1 ml of 0.3 *M* N, N, N', N', tetrakis (2-hydroxy propyl) ethylene diamine, shaken for 15 seconds and then allowed to stand for 10 minutes. 1 ml of buffer solution was added, strength of which was previously so adjusted that pH of the solution, when the volume was made upto the mark, was 6.0 ± 0.2 . The pink colour of the reaction mixture was read on Bausch and Lomb Colorimeter at 506 μ .

A standard solution of manganese was prepared as follows. 4.06 g $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (A. R.) was dissolved in water and made to one litre. 10 ml of this solution was further diluted to 500 ml (20 ppm). 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 ml of it was transferred to different 10 ml volumetric flasks and each was diluted to about 5 ml. 1 ml of 0.3*M* THPED solution was added to each flask and the unstoppered flasks were shaken rapidly for about 15 seconds to ensure a free mixing with air. The solution was allowed to stand for 10 minutes and then mixed with acetate buffer (ca 1 ml) sufficient to produce a pH of 6.0 ± 0.2 . The volume was made upto the mark with distilled water. Thorough mixing was done and transmittance was measured at 506 μ immediately using a reagent blank. The transmittance was plotted as a function of the manganese concentration.

Separation of Iron: Fit up the resin column as already mentioned and pass the extract from the Schöniger flask through the column. Mn is eluted by using 12 ml of 10 *N* HCl in 2 ml portions.

In the present communication to test the efficiency of the above procedure a solution of such dilution was taken so that 1 ml aliquot contained 0.8 mg of Mn. This was mixed with ferric chloride containing iron 20 times that of the manganese content. Placed a 3 ml aliquot of it in an ion exchange column which had been conditioned previously with 10 N HCl. When the aliquot had been passed into the resin bed, it was eluted with 12 ml of 10 N HCl in 2 ml portions. The effluent was evaporated to dryness and then transferred to a 10 ml flask and analysed for Mn as described in the recommended procedure for preparation of calibration curve. Recovery of Mn through an ion exchange column was found to be 100%.

The results obtained are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Manganese content of plants and food material

Name of material	Mn content by Quadrol method (ppm)	Mn content by Periodate method (ppm)
FOOD		
Brinjal	77.7	77.5
Cabbage	182.0	183.0
Wheat flour	81.2	80.0
Cauliflower	166.0	166.0
PLANT		
Citrus (Chloretic)	19.2	18.0
Maize	107.5	102.0

A reference to Table I indicates that the values obtained by THPED method are in good agreement with Periodate Method. The results obtained are reproducible and the mean deviation was found to be $\pm 0.62\%$. The standard deviation was $\pm 0.85\%$. In order to test the accuracy of this method, solutions containing known amounts of manganese were taken and on analysis by this method, the recovery was found to be 100 ± 0.85 .

The authors are grateful to Dr. Le Roy Pike of the Appalachian State Teachers College, Boone N.C. (U.S.A.) and to M/s Wyandotte Chemicals Corporation, U.S.A. for their gift of the N, N, N', N', tetrakis (2-hydroxy propyl) ethylene diamine (Quadrol) used in this work. Grateful thanks are also due to Dr. I. S. Bhatia, Professor and Head of the Depts. of Chemistry and Biochemistry for the inspiration and help given during the course of this investigation.

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Received, June 23, 1967.